

1 **Supplementary information to “Fate of intravenously administered umbilical cord**
2 **mesenchymal stromal cells and interactions with the host's immune system”**

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4 **Supplementary Figure 1| Images of the NOD/SCID animal administered with UC-MSCs from**
5 **donor 2, which displayed a persistent signal. (a)** Representative bioluminescence images of the
6 NOD/SCID mouse from 5 to 31 days post administration of FLuc⁺ UC-MSCs donor 2 (radiance scale
7 from 0.3×10^4 to 2×10^4 p/s/cm²/sr). **(b)** Light output (flux) as a function of time (days) for this specific
8 animal, overlaid with the average signal obtained from the other 4 NOD/SCID animals administered with
9 UC-MSCs from the same donor. Data for the average signal are displayed as mean \pm SD from $n = 4$.

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11 **Supplementary Table 1:** Specification of the antibodies employed for flow cytometry.

Antibody	Fluorochrome	Supplier	Clone	Dilution Factor
B220	APC-Vio770	Miltenyi	RA3-6B2	1:10
CD3ε	APC-Vio770	Miltenyi	145-2C1	1:50
CD4	VioBlue	Miltenyi	REA604	1:50
CD8	FITC	Miltenyi	53-6.7	1:50
CD11b	VioBlue	Miltenyi	M1/70.15.11.5	1:50
CD11c	PE	Miltenyi	N418	1:50
CD19	PE	Miltenyi	6D5	1:50
CD25	PE	eBioscience	PC61.5	1:200
CD68	PE	Miltenyi	FA-11	1:10
F4/80	APC	Miltenyi	REA126	1:50
FoxP3	APC	Miltenyi	REA788	1:50
Gr-1	APC-Vio770	Miltenyi	REA810	1:50
Ly6b	FITC	Miltenyi	REA115	1:10
NKp46	FITC	Miltenyi	29A1.4.9	1:50
Siglec H	FITC	Miltenyi	551.3D3	1:10

12 **Supplementary Table 2:** Number of SCID animals displaying detectable signal (n = 5 animals
13 per donor).

Donor	Day 5	Day 7	Day 10	Day 14	Day 17	Day 21	Day 24	Day 28	Day 31
1-727R	5	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	0
2-733S	4	3	3	2	0	0	0	0	0
3-735O	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

14 **Supplementary Table 3:** Number of NOD/SCID animals displaying detectable signal (n = 5
15 animals per donor)

Donor	Day 5	Day 7	Day 10	Day 14	Day 17	Day 21	Day 24	Day 28	Day 31
1-727R	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2-733S	5	5	5	5	3	1	1	1	1
3-735O*	4	4	4	2	0	0	0	0	0

16 * n = 4